

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INTERACTIVE GAMES IN LITERATURE LESSONS

Sapaeva Vazirakhon

Urgench Innovation University

Teacher of the Faculty of "Social and Humanities and Pedagogy".

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Annotation: This article provides information about the role and importance of interactive games in literature classes

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Today, the formation of new social relations in our society, the integration of education into the world education system requires a new approach to modern pedagogical technologies. These approaches, in turn, bring certain positive changes to the organizational and methodological aspects of the educational process, many of which are inextricably linked with pedagogical technology and pedagogical skills. It is known that today there are more than a hundred types of interactive methods, most of which have been tested and have given good results. Effective results can be achieved in the lesson by using the widely used methods - "Cluster", "Brainstorming", "Continue", "Presentation", "Blitz survey", "Problem situation". "Sinquain", "Reverse Test", "Wheel of Mind" methods are used in the part of the lesson to ask about the passed topic, "Insert", "Pinboard", "Zinama-zina", "Boomerang" technologies in the part of explaining the new topic, in the part of strengthening the topic Graphic organizers such as Venn Diagram, Fishbone, Why?, How?, Concept Chart, Lily Flower, and Concept Analysis, T-Table, Resume, The use of "Sunflower", "Charkhpalak" methods, "FSMU", "Cluster", "BBXB" methods for homework help to ensure the effectiveness of the lesson and increase the knowledge of students. In addition to the above-mentioned interactive methods, didactic games such as "Yes... no", "Find the owner of the definition", "Who am I?", "Domino" can be used in the native language and literature classes. During the game, students behave freely and want to show their knowledge. As a result, the student gains confidence and determination. Learns to engage in debate. He is used to justifying his opinion. The age and level of education of students should be taken into account. It is up to the teacher and the student to choose the technology to achieve the goal, because the main goal of both parties is to achieve a specific result, and the technology used is selected depending on the level of knowledge of the students, the nature of the group, and the situation. "Charkhpalak". This technology can teach students to remember the topics covered, to think logically, to independently answer the questions correctly and to self-assess, and in a short time, the teacher will teach all the students aimed at evaluating knowledge. The purpose of using this method is to teach students to think logically during the lesson, to be able to express their thoughts independently, to evaluate themselves, to work individually and in groups, to respect the opinions of others, to choose the right one from many opinions. is to teach. This technology is designed to evaluate, repeat, and strengthen the level of mastery of the subject

taught by students at the beginning and end of native language and literature classes or at the end of any section. "Charkhpalak" technology is implemented as follows:

- students are divided into groups depending on the conditions;
- handouts are distributed to group members;
- within the specified time, the groups complete the task in the handout, put the group number in the right corner, and their symbol in the left corner, exchange this handout to the key group in the direction of "turning the wheel";
- other group members also perform the tasks in the handout and make changes;
- after the last exchange of material, each group chooses the handout they filled out for the first time based on their symbol;
- the teacher reads the tasks given in the handout and determines the correct answer together with the team, or the tasks in the handout are highlighted on the screen and the correct answer is mentioned;
- each student identifies the differences in their answers marked with the correct answer and evaluates themselves.

Students can be given the following task for training using "Charkhpalak" technology: "Presentation" method. In this way, it is possible to organize repetition lessons held at the end of a certain topic or section. In this, students work individually, in pairs or in groups, independently search for a given topic, collect materials, sort them, select the main ones and make a presentation. For example, when a presentation lesson is held on the topic "Life and work of Alisher Navoi", the students are divided into groups and given a presentation in the following directions:

Group 1. Explain the life and activities of Alisher Navoi based on a chronological table.

Group 2. Explain the work of Alisher Navoi based on the "Cluster" method.

Group 3. Explain Alisher Navoi's lyrics based on the "Sunflower" method.

Group 4. Explain Alisher Navoi's "Khamsa" on the basis of a concept chart.

Each group collects information using textbooks and additional literature on given directions and makes a presentation through slides or drawings. Through the "Presentation" lessons, students can develop the following skills:

- express one's opinion in a clear and understandable way orally and in writing;
- to be able to use information sources, to create a database by searching for, analyzing and sorting the necessary information;
- having qualities such as learning by reading, improving one's knowledge independently, discussing what one has learned with friends, and being able to control oneself;
- understanding one's place in class and society, etc. Choice is optional, execution is mandatory" method.

In this case, students should voluntarily complete the tasks given in the exercise in the textbook on the basis of works of art, texts and materials from other textbooks. As a result, students develop the skills to learn independently, to show their interests and abilities. In the "Imkoniyat" method, at the end of the semester, students with high mastery are assigned to prepare tests for which the answers are selected and the answers are written. Students who have performed this task perfectly will be exempted from submitting the final control work. The following skills are formed in the students who took the test compared to the student who solved the test:

- being able to express one's opinion in writing in a consistent, clear and understandable way;

- to answer questions based on the topic and to be able to ask questions logically;

- ability to search, sort, select and analyze information;

- such as improving knowledge independently and being able to apply it in practice.

5 answers to 5 questions" method. This method can be used in mother tongue classes when studying the subject of "Compound Sentences". In this case, the handout or on the screen will bring to the students' attention the sentences in the form of test answers:

A. He who loves work will appreciate it.

B. Love is an old thing, but every heart makes it new.

D. Dreams are great, lives are short.

E. We artistically evaluate the events we have seen, heard, but ignored.

The table is distributed to the students. They mark the answers to the table. The students' answers are checked and their scores are summarized and evaluated. "Continue" method. This method not only teaches students to think quickly, but also develops their memory skills and develops the ability to work with textbooks. The task for the "Continue" method is organized as follows: the teacher gives the main words of the information related to the topic, and the student finds the continuation words of these words from the given text or piece of art work and completes the sentence. will do This method can be applied after studying the topic "O'tkir Hashimov's life and work". it is possible to express one's opinion freely, to respect the opinions of others, to develop the ability to defend one's point of view. establishment of mutual cooperation in the field of lim has led to great achievements.

In the short period of time after independence, there have been great changes in the education system, we have had extensive discoveries and achievements. It is known that science and education always develop together and change. Our government is paying great attention to the issues of further development of the education system, training on the basis of modern methods and technologies, with a deep study of the experience of foreign countries. It is no exaggeration to say that the introduction of innovative and pedagogical technologies into the education sector of our country was a turning point in education. Innovative technology and methods in this educational process, the main manager - teacher, managed - student activities are directed together, and in this process, the teacher and the student require the qualities of independence and creativity.

In this process, the teacher creates an environment for the student's personal improvement, development, learning and education, and therefore also performs the function of management and direction. Innovation (English innovation) is innovation. Innovative technologies are a pedagogical process, as well as introduction of innovations and changes to the teacher's activity, and interactive methods are widely used in its implementation. Interactive methods are called group thinking, that is, they are methods of pedagogical influence and are a component of the educational content. It is important to note that bringing non-traditional lessons to the "Mother language and literature" classes and integrating them into the educational content, finding new ways of teaching, creates the basis for meeting the requirements of the State Education Standards. The role of "Mother language and literature" lessons is incomparable in the development of the human personality in all aspects, in awakening a sense of respect for universal and national values in the growing young

generation, in developing a sense of pride in the national language and the traditions of one's people.

Also, in the current period, the pedagogue of the 21st century is required not only to have theoretical knowledge, but also to convey this knowledge to the minds of students through more effective methods, to create a foundation for easy, thorough and quick assimilation of the given knowledge, to form logical thinking, creativity and fluency in the minds of students. Of course, such tasks are performed through innovative technologies and various interactive games. So, now the teacher is required to switch from a traditional lesson to a non-traditional lesson: The main directions of a non-traditional lesson:

- a) teaching students to think independently;
- b) to concentrate the student's thoughts on one point;
- d) to create a clear understanding of the fundamentals and achievements of science in students;
- e) applying the acquired knowledge in practice and teaching others, etc.

It is difficult to imagine non-traditional lessons without interactive methods and games, because these are the core of the lesson. Interactive', 'Game lesson', 'Discussion lesson', 'Travel lesson', 'Competition lesson', 'FSMU', 'Fish skeleton', 'Charkhpalak' are of particular importance in the educational process. . The interactive methods used in the lessons fulfill the important tasks of awakening students' feelings of love for their native language and country, raising them to the level of perfect literacy, and achieving logical, clear and complete speech. implies. The use of such interactive methods and games during the lesson depends primarily on the skills of the pedagogue. The reason is that the methods should be prepared a day before the lesson, the necessary visual aids, handouts, short questions and answers and tests, the formation of evaluation criteria, as well as the motivation and punishment of students, are desirable. Each method should be selected and prepared by dividing it into easy and difficult types, taking into account the age of the students, interests, the ratio of the number of boys and girls, whether the learning process is fast or relatively slow, abilities and advantages. will be done.

Because it is the task of the teacher not to tire the children and to give them a rest to the brain and muscles through intelligently selected 3-4 minute movement thoughts. Great attention should be paid to the forms of speech, conversation, story, independent work, written work, increasing social and political knowledge by connecting with the present time, relying on independent thought in the course of the lesson. Another aspect that should be taken into account is the use of computer technologies during the lessons of the mother tongue and literature. For this, first of all, the teacher must organize the classroom with the necessary equipment, then presentations, videos, short films, pictures on the topic. and should create examples of creativity or select and download quality ones from Internet sites. The main reason for this is that they help to expand students' creativity and worldview, develop visual learning, and of course make the educational process more interesting and better organized. This method helps to understand grammatically complex topics easily, to develop the ability of students to compose independent simple sentences to small texts through pictures, to visualize and better remember the life and work of literary figures, and to enjoy their works through the screen. is characterized by the fact that it helps Today, one of the important trends in the use of innovative technologies is the introduction of interactive education and training methods. Discussion: Innovative technologies further improve the

quality and efficiency of education, help to increase the learning activity of pupils and students in the center of the educational process, and ensure the integrity of the educational process.

To realize this goal, first of all, it is necessary for the teacher to be able to choose the technologies that achieve the goal, to ensure the integrity of the educational process. In addition to providing other information during the lesson, if the teacher shows additional information on the subject, such as Internet information, multimedia programs, tables, etc., it not only helps students to learn It increases the aspiration of students, but also helps students to develop their free reading at the level of demand, to fully master the subject as much as possible. As a result of the use of innovative technologies, the students' skills of free thinking, analysis, drawing conclusions, stating their ideas, being able to defend them in a reasonable way, healthy communication, discussion, and debate will be improved and formed. In conclusion, deep mastering of native language and literary science can be more thorough, easier and faster through the rational use of interactive methods, games and computer technologies used by modern pedagogues

References:

1. Shayxislamov, N. Ona tili va adabiyot darslarida zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarni qo'llash mahorati. Science and Education, 2020.
2. Shayxislamov, N., Baykabilov, U. Til – millatning ma'naviy merosi. Tilning leksiksemantik tizimi, qiyosiy tipologik izlanishlar va adabiyotshunoslik muammolari, 2020.
3. Xolbekov, S. B. Adabiyot darslarida interfaol metodlardan foydalanish samarasi. Science and Education, 2020.
4. Rafiyev A., G'ulomova N. Ona tili va adabiyot (kasb-hunar kollejlari uchun darslik). T., "Sharq", 2013.
5. Sayidahmedov N. "Pedagogik mahorat va pedagogik texnologiya". – T.: 2003